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RENAL CARCINOMA IN A HOLLAND LOP RABBIT (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*)

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ABSTRACT

A 5-year-old intact female Holland Lop rabbit was presented for a routine health assessment prior to an elective ovariohysterectomy (OHE). Comprehensive physical examinations, along with haematologic and biochemical profiles revealed no abnormalities, and the patient was deemed fit for surgery. Intraoperatively, a well-vascularised, lobulated mass with a smooth surface and reddish discolouration, measuring 3×3×4 cm, was unexpectedly discovered in the left kidney during removal of the left ovary for routine OHE. The entire affected kidney was surgically excised, and the mass was submitted for histopathology, which confirmed a diagnosis of renal carcinoma. Postoperative care included renal support supplementation and scheduled follow-up assessments. Serial blood work and thoracoabdominal radiographs were performed to monitor renal function and screen for metastasis, respectively. As to date, the patient remains clinically stable, with no evidence of recurrence or metastasis. Renal carcinoma is a rare neoplasm in rabbits, with limited documentation available. This report details the histopathological characteristics of the tumour and provides insights into postoperative management and prognosis. Early detection through imaging or incidental surgical findings, and timely surgical intervention, may improve clinical outcomes in similar cases. Through the documentation of this case, we seek to contribute to the growing body of knowledge in lagomorph oncology and support veterinary clinicians in addressing future occurrences.

Keywords: histopathology; neoplasm; postoperative management; rabbit; renal carcinoma

INTRODUCTION

Renal carcinoma is a malignant epithelial neoplasm that originates from the renal tubular epithelium. In domestic animals, it is considered uncommon, representing less than 1% of all reported neoplasms in dogs and cats [1]. Among exotic companion mammals, particularly rabbits, reports of renal carcinoma are exceedingly rare, with only a handful of documented cases in the veterinary literature [2-4].

The clinical presentation in rabbits may be highly variable. Some patients remain asymptomatic until the disease is advanced, while others may present with nonspecific signs including weight loss, anorexia, haematuria, pollakiuria, lethargy, or abdominal distension [1]. In many cases, the tumour is detected incidentally during imaging or surgery, as in the one described here. Diagnosis requires histopathological evaluation, as imaging and gross findings alone are insufficient to differentiate renal carcinoma from other renal neoplasms or inflammatory lesions [1,5].

Due to the paucity of published cases, there is a lack of knowledge regarding the biological behaviour, metastatic potential, and prognosis of renal carcinoma in rabbits. Early recognition and surgical intervention may provide favourable outcomes, but long-term follow-up is essential to determine

recurrence or metastasis. This report describes an incidental finding of a renal carcinoma in a Holland Lop rabbit undergoing elective ovariohysterectomy (OHE), with emphasis on the histopathological characteristics and postoperative management considerations.

SIGNALMENT AND HISTORY

A 5-year-old intact female Holland Lop rabbit was presented to the veterinary clinic for a routine health assessment prior to an elective ovariohysterectomy (OHE). The rabbit was housed indoors as a companion animal, maintained on a balanced diet of timothy hay and pellets, and reported by the owner to be bright, alert, and responsive, with a favourable appetite, normal urination and defecation, and no recent history of illness or clinical abnormalities.

PHYSICAL EXAMINATION AND PREOPERATIVE ASSESSMENT

On presentation, the rabbit's body condition score was ideal, and the vital parameters were within normal limits. A complete physical examination did not reveal any abnormalities. Preoperative haematologic and serum biochemical profiles, including renal and hepatic parameters, were within normal reference ranges. Based on these findings, the patient was deemed fit for an elective OHE under general anaesthesia.

SURGICAL FINDINGS

Routine midline laparotomy was performed under aseptic conditions. During removal of the left ovary, an abnormal structure was incidentally discovered in the region of the left kidney. Careful exploration revealed a well-vascularised, lobulated mass with a smooth surface and reddish discolouration, measuring approximately $3 \times 3 \times 4$ cm (Figures 1 & 2). The mass appeared to be diffused and arise from the left kidney.

Figure 1. Approximately a mass of $3 \times 3 \times 4$ cm was removed.

Figure 2. A well-vascularised, lobulated mass with a smooth surface and reddish discolouration.

Figure 3. Cross-section of the resected mass.

A unilateral nephrectomy was performed due to the appearance and location of the mass. The renal vessels and ureter were carefully ligated, and the entire affected kidney with the mass was removed. Haemostasis was achieved using haemoclips, and the ovariectomy was completed

uneventfully. The patient recovered smoothly from anaesthesia.

HISTOPATHOLOGICAL EVALUATION

The resected kidney with the mass was submitted for histopathological analysis. The renal tissue exhibited a poorly demarcated, well-differentiated, transitioning from tubular-to-solid neoplasm, which compresses the adjacent parenchyma (Figure 4). The neoplasm is composed of disorganised tubules embedded in a loose, pale eosinophilic, collagenous matrix. The tubular epithelial lining consists of one to several layers of cuboidal to cylindrical cells. In localised areas, epithelial cells are tightly arranged, forming a solid pattern. Some lumina contain fibrillar or homogeneous secretory material. Ectatic tubules are prevalent and create cystic spaces. Mitotic figures are infrequent, and multifocal necroses are evident (Figures 5 & 6). These findings validate the diagnosis of renal carcinoma [1].

Figure 4: Tubular to solid neoplasm compressing adjacent normal renal parenchyma (H&E stain, 100×).

Figure 5: Loose, pale eosinophilic, collagenous matrix featuring disorganised tubules (H&E stain, 100×).

Figure 6: Higher magnification of multifocal necrosis of the neoplasm (H&E stain, 200×).

POSTOPERATIVE MANAGEMENT AND FOLLOW-UP

Postoperative care included procaine penicillin (150 mg/mL) and benzathine penicillin (115 mg/mL) (Duplocillin® 265 mg/mL injection, Intervet Australia Pty Ltd., Bendigo East, Victoria, Australia) administered subcutaneously at 32.5 mg/kg, given twice at 48-hour intervals. Enrofloxacin (ENFLOX-100® 100 mg/mL oral solution, Pahang Pharmacy Sdn. Bhd., Malaysia) was then administered orally at 10 mg/kg twice daily for seven days. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory (NSAID), meloxicam (Rheumocam® 1.5 mg/mL oral suspension, Chanelle Pharma, Loughrea, Ireland) was given orally at 0.5 mg/kg once daily for seven days. Dehydration and electrolyte imbalanced were addressed by infusing Compound Sodium Lactate solution (Infusol® HM, Hartmann's solution, Ain Medicare Sdn. Bhd., Malaysia) at 50 mL/kg intravenously for one day. The rabbit's appetite and activity levels returned to normal within 72 hours post-surgery, and the recovery was otherwise unremarkable.

A urinary support supplement (Renalof®, containing *Cynodon dactylon* (Bermuda grass) as the active ingredient, was prescribed for continuous management due to its purported efficacy in enhancing the renal function, reducing oxidative stress, and alleviating the progression of renal disease

[7,8]. The owner was instructed to observe for alterations in urine output, fluid consumption, appetite, or behaviour.

Follow-up assessments were scheduled every 3–6 months. Serial blood work was performed to evaluate renal parameters and overall health status. Thoracoabdominal radiographs were performed to detect for metastasis, particularly in the lungs, liver, and contralateral kidney. As to date, approximately 15 months post-operatively, the rabbit remains clinically stable with no evidence of recurrence or metastasis.

DISCUSSION

Renal tumours are uncommon in domestic animals, and even more so in rabbits [1-4]. Renal carcinoma is the most documented primary malignant tumour of the kidney among renal neoplasms [1]. In dogs and cats, renal carcinomas are often locally invasive and have the potential to metastasise to the contralateral kidney, lungs, liver, and regional lymph nodes [1,4]. However, the biological behaviour in rabbits remains poorly documented due to a scarcity of cases.

In rabbits, the clinical manifestations of renal neoplasia are often nonspecific, resulting in a delayed diagnosis until the disease has advanced. In the present case, the renal carcinoma was incidentally discovered during OHE prior to the manifestation of

clinical signs or metastasis. This is consistent with previous reports noting that numerous renal tumours in rabbits remain asymptomatic until they reach an advanced stage or detected incidentally [3,6]. The absence of abnormalities on preoperative bloodwork supports the observation that early-stage renal tumours may not affect standard haematology or biochemistry profiles.

Surgical excision via nephrectomy remains the primary therapeutic approach for localised renal carcinoma. Rabbits can tolerate unilateral nephrectomy, provided the contralateral kidney is healthy [5]. The procedure was well tolerated, and the patient experienced an uneventful recovery.

Histopathology yields a definitive diagnosis in this instance. In canine renal tumours, mitotic count (MC) has been identified as one of the most reliable prognostic indicators of biological behaviour. Studies have shown that tumours with higher MC values are associated with significantly shorter survival times, while those with lower MC often carry a more favourable prognosis [1]. Although equivalent prognostic thresholds have not yet been established in rabbits due to the rarity of reported cases, it is reasonable to extrapolate from canine data that the low mitotic activity observed in this case may be indicative of a less aggressive tumour. This suggestion is

further supported by the absence of recurrence or metastasis during follow-up, suggesting that histopathological evaluation of MC may also have predictive value in lagomorph renal neoplasia.

Adjunctive management included Renalof®, a supplement derived from *Cynodon dactylon* (Bermuda grass). Experimental studies in rodent models suggest that aqueous extracts of *C. dactylon* have nephroprotective properties [7]. In streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats, supplementation reduced elevated creatinine and blood urea levels, restored total protein, and preserved renal histology. Other work demonstrated that *C. dactylon* extracts reduced calcium oxalate deposition and increased serum antioxidant activity in rat models of nephrolithiasis [8]. While these findings are promising, they derive from non-neoplastic renal disease in rodents, and direct applicability to rabbits with renal carcinoma remains unproven.

Therefore, in this case, the use of *C. dactylon* should be considered supportive rather than curative. The supplement may have contributed to maintaining renal function in the contralateral kidney post-nephrectomy, but the favourable long-term outcome (15 months disease-free) was likely due to complete surgical excision at an early stage. Adjuvant therapies such as chemotherapy or

radiation have not been well studied in rabbits, and their role in the management of renal carcinoma is currently unknown. Nonetheless, chemotherapy is not regarded as effective in the treatment of renal neoplasia in other species [5, 6].

The prognosis for renal carcinoma in rabbits is difficult to determine due to the limited number of reported cases. In dogs and cats, the prognosis depends on the extent of local invasion and presence of metastasis at the time of diagnosis. The prognosis is typically unfavourable following the onset of metastasis [1]. The absence of recurrence or metastasis during follow-up indicates a positive short-term prognosis. Continuous monitoring is crucial, as renal carcinomas may metastasise later in the disease progression. Ongoing documentation of these cases is essential to determine prognosis, optimal treatment approaches, and adjunctive therapies for renal neoplasia in lagomorphs.

CONCLUSION

Renal carcinoma is a rare neoplasm in rabbits, with limited documentation in the literature. This report highlights the histopathological characteristics of the tumour and provides insights into post-operative management and prognosis. Early detection through imaging or incidental surgical findings, prompt surgical

intervention, and diligent post-operative monitoring can yield favourable outcomes in similar cases. Documenting these cases is critical for enhancing clinical understanding and directing the management of renal neoplasia in lagomorphs.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

All authors have declared no conflict of interest that is relevant to this case report.

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